

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Cuba

Version 1

**International
Science Council**

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About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the [World Data System](#) (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) [Policy Series](#) reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

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Acronyms

CITMA	Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment
SPP	System of Programs and Projects

Introduction

In Cuba there isn't a national policy for research data management. There are no research data repositories either, and the researchers who wish to make their data accessible deposit them in global repositories such as Zenodo or in data repositories of certain disciplines, such as those related to Biodiversity.

The Programs and Projects System (SPP) groups science, technology, and innovation projects, whether or not associated with programs, according to their priority level, and which contribute to the country's economic and social development (Ministro de Ciencia, Tecnología y Medio Ambiente, 2025). More than 6,000 science, technology and innovation projects are currently being implemented, mainly financed with public funds, whose results and data sets are not accessible. This makes reproducibility and transparency of research and the reuse of data and collaboration between institutions and researchers difficult.

This proposed Research Data Management Policy aims to create avenues for sharing and making accessible knowledge, promoting transparency and scientific collaboration.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies

It is recommended that science, technology, and innovation projects funded with public funds through the Programs and Projects System submit, within a maximum of six months after approval, the first version of the Research Data Management Plan. This plan describes the processing of collected or generated research data and serves as the basis for scientific and technical reports and scientific publications.

Scientific data generated by science, technology, and innovation projects and their metadata must be deposited in an appropriate data repository¹, under a license that allows access, extraction, and reproduction of the data and their metadata. The repository must also provide information on the software tools and instruments needed to use and validate the data, and, where possible, provide them.

Exceptionally, there is no obligation to deposit or provide access to research data subject to confidentiality agreements, undisclosed information, and information subject to protection by industrial property; as well as information whose disclosure may affect national security, the right to privacy and respect for human subjects, personal data, the protection of rare, threatened, or endangered species, and other information contemplated in current regulations.

¹A suitable data repository provides open public access to research data, allows citation through persistent identifiers, provides quality metadata, and complies with accepted guidelines and standards.

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